

JURISPRUDENCE

MAIN ASPECTS OF THE LEGAL-JUDICIAL SYSTEM IN THE ILKHANATE STATE

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Abstract

The Ilkhanate (Hulaguids) state and its legal-judicial system represent a significant stage in the centuries-old history of statehood and law in Azerbaijan. Covering the 13th to 14th centuries, this period reflects important developments in governance and law, as well as the formation of the Islamic legal system. This topic remains relevant for exploring the historical roots of modern legal systems. The influence of political and legal movements on the legal system in the medieval Islamic East during this era is noteworthy. The Ilkhanate state marks an important milestone in the development of law and statehood in Azerbaijani history, and the study of this field continues to be of great significance.

Keywords: Ilkhanate, court, faqih, legal system, ruler, Muslim, decree, civil, property, state, Islam, Muslim jurisprudence

Introduction

The development of law in Azerbaijan during the 13th and 14th centuries, specifically the legal system of the Ilkhanate state, can be divided into two periods. The first period (approximately 1256–1294) was influenced by the Yassa of Genghis Khan, while the second period (1294–1357) was characterized by the predominance of Islamic Sharia law. However, this duality was not always absolute. During the initial Mongol invasions, the legal and judicial activities of Muslims were not interfered with by the Mongols. The establishment of the office of Qazi al-Qudat (Chief Judge), the appointment of the Qazi al-Qudat by the ruler, and the subordination of qazis solely to Sharia law as a result of reforms by Ghazan Khan did not entirely eliminate this legal duality.

In the history of Islam, the legal relations of the state were regulated by two main systems: state laws and Sharia laws. Secular rulers tended to avoid confrontations with the faqihs (Islamic jurists) and sometimes refrained from undermining their authority due to their own weak positions or religious affiliations. However, rulers sought to concentrate legislative powers in their hands, while faqihs attempted to limit the rulers' authority. Before and after the 13th-14th centuries, an unwritten division of powers existed in the legal field: Sharia courts and state courts, Sharia qazis and state-appointed qazis operated in parallel. Matters such as marriage, worship, family, inheritance, and divorce primarily fell under the jurisdiction of Sharia courts, whereas political, commercial, financial, and administrative issues were resolved by state courts. State courts relied on the decrees of the ruler, while Sharia courts based their decisions on Sharia sanctions (5, p.59).

Muslim Law (Fiqh) During the Ilkhanate Period

Muslim law (fiqh) encompassed most aspects of social life during the Ilkhanate era. However, in certain legal areas, the state played a primary role. There were no significant changes in Muslim law before and after the Hulaguids period. Islamic law, based on the Qur'an and sacred traditions, initially existed alongside ethical and moral norms as well as rules of worship; later, worship and legal norms became distinct (6, p.135).

The legal doctrines and institutions developed by Muslim jurists over centuries evolved differently depending on various religious madhhabs (schools of thought). Their works systematically covered civil law, family law, criminal law, and judicial procedures.

In Muslim civil law, property and non-property relations were regulated without discrimination. The state was not the subject of law but acted solely as its executor; the creator of law was Allah. Islamic religion and jurisprudence required rulers to be no different from ordinary Muslims. In Muslim civil law, there is no statute of limitations on claims; anyone may demand their property at any time. Sharia courts do not adjudicate disputes over prohibited items (e.g., pork, wine); instead, they impose penalties on the owners.

Muslim law places great emphasis on trade and defines the terms of commercial contracts. The rights and duties of buyers and sellers in trade are clearly regulated. Traditionally, contracts were oral, requiring witnesses to be present. Lease and rental agreements also hold an important place in Muslim law; the right to use property is granted without transferring ownership.

The Qur'an permits pledges in loan agreements, but the value of the pledge must not be less than the loan amount, and prohibited items may not be used as collateral (3, p.172). Both the pledgor and pledgee must meet certain requirements. Guardianship applies to bankrupt, minor, immoral, and mentally ill persons; the

duties and responsibilities of guardians are specified in detail.

In Islamic law, agency (*wakālah*) is a contract concluded between legally capable persons. Both the agent and the principal must meet specific conditions, and the contract must be formalized in the presence of witnesses. Agency is used in marriage, divorce, inheritance, trade, and other legal transactions (2).

Muslim civil law also includes legal institutions such as usufruct (*aria* – the right to use property without compensation). Usurpation and loan agreements are also addressed by *fiqh*. Legal protection and penalties are established for cases of usurpation. Lending is considered one of the most virtuous acts among Muslims (4, p.201).

Debt, Waqf, Gift, Lost Property, and Other Civil Law Relations in Islamic Law

A debt contract is concluded in the form of money, specifying the exact amount and the repayment period in the agreement. It is strictly forbidden to use debt for usury, profit, seizure, or ostentation. The contract does not specify the purpose for which the debt will be spent; however, obligations such as providing property of equal value in exchange for the debt, working for the lender, or employing a slave may be stipulated. The debtor must repay the money on time, while the lender should neither pressure nor disrespect the debtor. The debt contract can be concluded either directly by the parties themselves or through their representatives. The contract is terminated when the debt is repaid or compensated.

Waqf (endowment) holds a significant place in Islamic civil law. Waqf refers to property donated by the state or individuals for charitable purposes to a special administration. Items considered *haram* or impure, sick slaves, indivisible property, and wealth obtained unlawfully cannot be donated as waqf. Property given as waqf cannot be sold, gifted, or exchanged. Such property is used to meet the needs of religious institutions, national scholars, and the poor. Infidels and apostates are not permitted to use waqf properties. If it is impossible to maintain the waqf property, it may be rejected. The location of the waqf property must be precisely specified; for example, it must be clear whether a slave girl belongs to a mosque or a madrasa. Property acquired in the form of debt cannot be endowed as waqf. The person managing the waqf property is called the "mutawalli" (3, p.211).

Gift Giving and Lost Property in Islamic Law

Gift giving is regulated in the *Kitab al-Hibah* (Book of Gifts) section of *fiqh* and closely aligns with modern legal norms. A gift is a unilateral contract and must not be given with malicious intent. No demands or conditions can be imposed in return for a gift. Gifts may be given in written or oral form, and the gifted item must be delivered immediately. For example, freeing a slave or granting freedom to a concubine to marry counts as a gift; however, the giver cannot later change their mind and reclaim the slave. Both the giver and the recipient must possess legal capacity. Stolen, usurped, or prohibited (*haram*) items cannot be objects of a gift. Gifts may be made to an individual, to a waqf, or to a group of people (2, p.432).

The discovery and return of lost property are explained within the *hibbah* section of Islamic law. A Muslim who finds lost property must immediately seek its owner and return the item; misappropriation is considered forbidden (*haram*). A legally competent person who finds movable or immovable property must promptly deliver it either to the owner or to the appropriate authority. If the finder is a slave or concubine, their master must hold the property and return it to its owner. The custodian is obligated to protect the item from damage; if the property is an animal, it must be fed. Once ownership is proven, the property is returned to the owner. Costs incurred for safekeeping and services rendered may be claimed from the owner. If a reward was promised to the finder, it must be paid. The custody period is one year; if the property remains ownerless during this time, it is allocated to public needs by decision of the *bayt al-mal* (public treasury) or community authorities.

Military Booty, War Spoils, and Inheritance in Islamic Law

Military booty and spoils of war fall under the domain of civil law in Islamic jurisprudence. According to the *Kitab al-Ghanimah* (Book of Booty), captives and property seized during wars against infidels are considered spoils of war. Their distribution is the responsibility of the Muslim community, not the state. These legal norms, established during the Prophet's time, were applied during military campaigns of Islamic armies (2).

War spoils consist of various taxes (such as *jiyya*—the poll tax, *zakat*, and *kharaj*) and property belonging to the *dhimmi* (non-Muslim subjects under Muslim rule), which are allocated to the administration of *Dar al-Islam* (the Muslim state). Immovable property is designated as *waqf* (endowment), while movable property is distributed to the poor, the sick, families of those participating in *jihad*, and for the maintenance of mosques. Weapons and other equipment seized from infidels during battle are distributed among the soldiers. One-fifth of the booty is given to *Dar al-Islam*, while the remaining four-fifths are equally divided among the warriors. The share of a deceased soldier is given to their family. This distribution system serves as a motivation for the fighters (7, p.324).

The institution of inheritance holds significant importance in Islamic law. *Fiqh* regulates inheritance rights as a civil contract alongside wills. The principles of inheritance are outlined in the Qur'an, especially in verse 176 of Surah An-Nisa, and Muslim jurists have developed these principles into a comprehensive legal system (1, p.48). Unborn children and freed slaves also possess inheritance rights. Inheritance is of two types: by will (*wasiyyah*) and by law. A person making a will may gift up to one-third of their estate to a chosen individual; however, such a will cannot contravene the rights of legal heirs. Wills must be made in written or oral form in the presence of two witnesses. Two-thirds of the inheritance is divided among the legal heirs after deducting debts and expenses. Women's shares of inheritance are less than those of men. Heirs are obligated to settle all debts and obligations of the deceased, free

their slaves, and pay *khums* and *zakat* before distributing the inheritance.

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